

Open Science Implementation Plan for the Biodata Resource Inventory

The Biodata Resource Inventory project follows the practices of Open Science for the sake of practical ability to update the Inventory in future years and to show a genuine commitment to Open Science principles. As a collaboration between the Chan Zuckerberg Initiative (CZI) and the Global Biodata Coalition (GCB) and its contractors, we outline our plans for implementing Open Science practices below. We commit to working collegially and flexibly with each other to achieve the aims below to the fullest extent possible. We acknowledge that as work in progress, we may have to revisit specific aims within this plan to adjust for project realities.

Reproducibility Standards

Reproducibility and related concepts have many [definitions](#), which are dependent on project context and goals. For the purpose of this project, we are modeling the ML reproducibility standards for the Life Sciences from Heil *et al.* [1]:

1. **Bronze Standard:** The authors make the data, models and code used in the analysis publicly available. The bronze standard is the minimal standard for reproducibility. Without data, models and code, it is not possible to reproduce a work.
2. **Silver standard:** In addition to meeting the bronze standard: (1) the dependencies of the analysis can be downloaded and installed in a single command; (2) key details for reproducing the work are documented, including the order in which to run the analysis scripts, the operating system used and system resource requirements; and (3) all random components in the analysis are set to be deterministic. The silver standard is a midway point between minimal availability and full automation. Works that meet this standard will take much less time to reproduce than ones only meeting the bronze standard.
3. **Gold standard:** The work meets the silver standard, and the authors make the analysis reproducible with a single command. The gold standard for reproducibility is full automation. When a work meets this standard, it will take little to no effort for a scientist to reproduce it.

We aim for the Gold Standard of reproducibility. Here is the plan to meet each standard:

- Dependency management:
 - Description of dependencies: dependencies and their versions described in both README and requirements.txt.
 - Automated installation: Conda (via environment YAML in repository).

- Containerization: Docker?
- For non-code dependencies (*e.g.* training data, trained models) also include a make target for downloading and setup such as unzipping.
- All of the above should be included, since sometimes Docker or conda may not be an option.
- Running the analysis:
 - Description of how to run the analysis in README.
 - Snakemake to automatically run the entire pipeline (including training, obtaining model performance results, and figure generation).
- Archiving and persistence:
 - All training data, code, and trained model should be archived (*e.g.* Zenodo).
 - All code will be stored on GitHub. We may want two repositories in the end:
 - One to reproduce the results in the paper entirely, including training, model selection and evaluation, and figure generation.
 - Another for reperforming the analysis later, such as retrieving the trained model and performing prediction.

Code Standards

To maintain confidence in the results, we will aim to make the code as robust and reproducible as possible. Additionally, to make the code valuable to the open science community, we will enforce community guidelines (*e.g.* we will adhere to PEP8 style guide for Python code [2]). Some criteria for program reproducibility can be found in Mastering Python for Bioinformatics by Clark, K.Y. [3]:

- *Parameters*: All program parameters can be set as runtime arguments. This means no hard-coded values which would require changing the source code to change the program's behavior.
- *Documentation*: A program should respond to a `--help` argument by printing the parameters and usage.
- *Testing*: You should be able to run a test suite that proves the code meets some specifications.

Here are the primary code standards, and how they can be enforced efficiently:

- *Linting*: All code must pass `pylint`, which enforces PEP8. The repository(ies) will hold the `.pylintrc` file, and additions to the `.pylintrc` file will be agreed upon. An auto formatter, such as `yapf`, greatly simplifies keeping code linted.
- *Static code-checking*: All code must pass `flake8`, which enforces PEP8.
- *Static type-checking*: All code must pass `mypy`, and type hints should be added throughout. Static type checking can be [great for preventing subtle bugs](#).
- *Testing*: Automated testing will be performed by `pytest`, including integration and unit tests. The tests describe how the programs should behave, and passing those tests proves that those descriptions are met. This is important for open science; it ensures that the community can

contribute to our project without introducing breaking changes. All of the above requirements will also be assessed with `pytest` through `pytest-pylint`, `pytest-flake8`, and `pytest-mypy`. A Make target (`make test`) should be added to simplify and standardize the testing procedure.

Other considerations:

- Scripts should be parameterized. This implies no hard-coded paths. Paths should be passed as parameters, such as via `argparse`.
- Since paths will need to be passed in, config files should be used so that automation can be performed using `Snakemake`. If paths change for another user, only config files need to be changed.
- Parameterize, but provide reasonable and useful defaults where possible for ease of use.

Data Standards

To maximize future utility of the data created through the GBC Biodata Resource Inventory, we aim to follow the [FAIR Principles of Data Management and Stewardship](#).

- F (Findable) & A (Accessible)
 - Input data: use Open Data sources wherever possible and access methods (e.g. source and query), access dates, etc. are documented; if open data cannot be used, indicate terms and conditions of access and how the data might be obtained by someone else (e.g. company, contact name, cost/fees).
 - New data products: As indicated above for code, new data products will be deposited in openly available, persistent archive(s) with metadata that is indexed in a central data store.
- I (Interoperable)
 - New data products reuse existing vocabularies, ontologies, schemas, and/or standards when available, including open identifiers (e.g. DOIs).
- R (Reuseable)
 - Provenance information is provided, including complete documentation that fully describes variables (e.g. expected values, limits, ranges, etc. as appropriate for data type) and processes (e.g., data cleaning methods)
 - New data products are consistently formatted, such that data are readily used/manipulated within programming/computational environments, and are made available in file formats that are readily opened, manipulated, and converted into other formats and/or structures
 - New data products are released as open data (CC0)

External Review/Validation

Review of Open Science products by an individual not deeply involved in the project increases the likelihood that someone else can make use of the products later. Such individuals are referred to by various communities as “reproducibility collaborators” (Heil et al in [1]) or “data curators” (Coburn and Johnson [3]), and this role is covered by [validation](#) in the CRediT taxonomy.

- Prior to releasing open code, data, etc., an external party (or parties) will review and cross-check documentation with available code and data, and will independently execute the code.
- Any individual(s) performing these validation steps will be listed in article acknowledgements and data/code documentation.

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Document Purpose and History

This document was created at the beginning of a project between the Global Biodata Coalition (GCB) and Chan Zuckerberg Initiative (CZI) to identify biodata resources in the scientific literature using machine learning methods. The document was drafted in early spring 2022 by KES and HJI (GBC) and then reviewed by CEC (GBC) and AMI and DL (CZI) at the launch of the collaboration. It was otherwise not modified or updated during the course of the project other than formatting for deposition on Zenodo. In preparation for deposit into GBC’s Zenodo collection, in fall 2022 HJI and CEC edited the document for clarity for external audiences, converted links in the references to Wayback URLs for better persistence, resolved comments, added this and the author statement.

References

1. Heil, B.J.; Hoffman, M.M.; Markowitz, F.; Lee, S.-I.; Greene, C.S.; Hicks, S.C. Reproducibility Standards for Machine Learning in the Life Sciences. *Nat Methods* **2021**, *18*, 1132–1135. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-021-01256-7>
2. Van Rossum, G.; Warsaw, B.; Coghlan, N. PEP 8—Style Guide for Python Code. *Python.org* **2001**, 1565. <https://web.archive.org/web/20221013023754/https://peps.python.org/pep-0008/>
3. Youens-Clark, K. *Mastering Python for Bioinformatics*; O’Reilly Media, Inc, 2021; ISBN 978-1-09-810088-9.
3. Coburn E, Johnston L. Testing Our Assumptions: Preliminary Results from the Data Curation Network. *Journal of eScience Librarianship* **2020**, 9, e1186. <https://doi.org/10.7191/jeslib.2020.1186>